

Soiling in the Atacama Desert: Impacts on solar performance and evaluation of cleaning techniques

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Photovoltaic
Soiling
Cementation
Desert
Cleaning strategy
Accelerated testing

ABSTRACT

Cemented soiling on photovoltaic modules poses a critical challenge to energy yield in arid and hyper-arid climates. Unlike loose dust, these hardened deposits form cohesive crusts that impair optical transmittance and accelerate surface degradation. This study combines outdoor exposure in the Atacama Desert with controlled laboratory replication to investigate the formation, evolution, and impact of cemented soiling on PV systems. Moving beyond previous research focused on loose particles, we highlight the role of gypsum recrystallization, quantify associated energy losses, and evaluate cleaning strategies in terms of recovery efficiency and long-term prevention. The dual methodology, real-world exposure and accelerated testing with desert dust, enables reproducible insights into cementation kinetics and cleaning effectiveness. Cementation began as early as day two, forming structured gypsum crystals by day seven. Transmittance losses stabilized at -0.827% per month, resulting in estimated annual losses of ~ 98 MWh per 10 MW plant ($\sim 9.8\%$). Cleaning tests showed that water-based methods restored 99.9% of the initial performance after one application, while dry methods restored 98.8% but left residues that promoted recrystallization. These findings offer actionable insights to optimize cleaning frequency and methods, supporting more efficient and sustainable PV operations in desert environments.

1. Introduction

Renewable energy sources (RE), particularly photovoltaic (PV) solar energy, have become a key alternative for a sustainable energy transition, reducing dependence on traditional energy sources such as coal, natural gas, oil, and nuclear power [1]. Over the past decade, the PV sector has experienced accelerated growth, driven by a sustained decrease in the cost of modules, electronic components, and auxiliary systems, enabling the installation of large-scale facilities and competitiveness in various markets [2,3].

The appeal of PV energy lies not only in its low environmental impact but also in its long-term economic viability [4]. One of the recent advances in PV module design is the increment of the PV cells size, which

has allowed for a larger active surface area per module and, consequently, higher nominal power output. This improvement lowers the balance of system (BOS) costs, enhances energy efficiency, and increases power density per unit area, further consolidating the competitiveness of this technology in both small- and large-scale applications [5]. The initial capital expenditure (CAPEX) comprises high costs, but the operation and maintenance costs (OPEX) correspond to a significant fraction of the total cost over the system's lifetime [6,7]. Thus OPEX a decisive factor in the overall profitability of PV plants [8].

Soiling, the accumulation of dust, salt, and other contaminants on the surface of PV modules, reduces the effective irradiance on the cells decreasing energy generation [9,10]. Its impact is not only technical but also economic, especially in arid and semi-arid environments, with

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.124815>

Received 20 August 2025; Received in revised form 12 November 2025; Accepted 26 November 2025

Available online 29 November 2025

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significant effects in OPEX costs. According to Mounir Abraim et al. [11], annual energy losses due to soiling can reach up to 0.24 %/day in desertic regions, such as Morocco (Semi-arid climate), even exceeding 50 % of annual losses in regions such as Niamey, Niger [12]. With an estimated cost of 4.6 cents per kilowatt-hour in certain scenarios, even exceeding the costs of maintenance or the natural degradation of the modules, these losses accumulated over time directly compromise the economic viability of solar plants.

Although soiling has traditionally been associated with the deposition of dry dust on the surface of modules, in certain regions with specific environmental conditions, such as high nocturnal relative humidity and the presence of soluble salts, this phenomenon can evolve into more complex forms [13,14]. Among them is cementation, a process in which fine particles and hygroscopic salts undergo daily cycles of dissolution and recrystallization that lead to the formation of hardened crusts with high surface cohesion [15–17]. These layers not only drastically reduce optical transmittance but also exhibit significant resistance to conventional cleaning methods. This type of dust deposition is a new operational challenge, due to the need for more frequent, intensive, and therefore more expensive cleaning interventions [18].

Dry cleaning techniques, such as mechanical brushes or compressed air, are generally cheaper and logistically simpler, however, their effectiveness against cemented layers is limited and may leave residues behind [18]. Conversely, pressurized water cleaning is more effective for adhered crusts removal, but presents significant challenges in terms of water availability, associated infrastructure (filtration, storage, and recirculation), and increased OPEX, especially in desertic regions [17–19].

While numerous studies have examined the effects of loose (non-cemented) dust on PV performance, very few have focused on cemented soiling, despite its increasing relevance in hyper-arid environments. Existing works have either relied solely on outdoor observations, which

limit reproducibility, or on laboratory tests that fail to capture the complexity of real-world conditions. The novelty of this study lies in its integrated approach: it combines (i) long-term real-field monitoring at the Atacama Desert, one of the most extreme PV exposure environments worldwide, with (ii) accelerated laboratory experiments that replicate cementation processes under controlled conditions. By linking these complementary research infrastructures, the outdoor Atacama Desert Solar Platform (PSDA) and the indoor soiling laboratory at CEA-INES, the study enables, for the first time, a systematic analysis of deposit formation, surface adhesion, cleaning responses, and recrystallization dynamics.

In this work we deepen the understanding of cemented soiling's formation and evolution under hyper-arid conditions and evaluate the relative effectiveness of dry and wet cleaning strategies. By explicitly connecting the morphology of the deposited dust, soiling environmental drivers, and cleaning performance, this study provides a comprehensive framework that not only advances scientific understanding of cementation mechanisms but also delivers practical guidance to design cost-effective maintenance protocols. These insights are critical to optimize both short-term performance recovery and long-term durability of PV systems in high-irradiance and high-soiling-risk desertic environments, making the work highly relevant for real-world PV plant operations.

2. Methodology

The experimental design was conceived as a comparative methodology integrating field observations and controlled laboratory experiments to reproduce and contrast the process of particulate material deposition and consolidation in desertic environments. This approach enabled the linkage between natural exposure conditions (subjected to environmental variability) with controlled scenarios in which the main factors involved in these processes could be isolated and reproduced. As

Fig. 1. Experimental workflow integrating outdoor and indoor methodologies used for the comparative analysis of dust deposition and cleaning processes on PV modules.

shown in Fig. 1 Experimental workflow integrating outdoor and indoor methodologies used for the comparative analysis of dust deposition and cleaning processes on PV modules. Fig. 1, the methodology framework establishes a direct association between deposition processes observed under outdoor conditions and those replicated under in the indoor experiment. In this way, the information obtained in the field is integrated with the data generated in the laboratory under reproducible parameters. Thus, this experimental framework enabled the evaluation of the cleaning strategies applied in this study through an indoor experiment that replicates the outdoor conditions. The details of both methodologies, the outdoor field characterization and the indoor controlled replication are described below.

2.1. Outdoor soiling characterization and performance assessment at PSDA

Outdoor experiments were carried out at the Atacama Desert Solar Platform (PSDA), an experimental facility operated by the University of Antofagasta (UA) for solar technology evaluation in desert conditions. The site (24.09° S, 69.93° W, 1000 m a.s.l.) is classified as cold arid (Bwk) according to Köppen-Geiger [20]. Meteorological data, including ambient temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, and global horizontal irradiance (GHI), were recorded using calibrated sensors (Young CS215-L11, HMP60-L11, Young 05103-5, CMP21) with 1-min averages, following WMO Guide No. 8 [21]. Data covers February–May 2025, capturing key atmospheric drivers of soiling.

To assess soiling evolution, PV glass coupons (4 × 6 cm) were mounted in triplicate on active PV modules (20° tilt, north-facing) and exposed outdoors (Fig. 2a and b). Samples were removed after 2 days, 1 week, 1, 2, and 3 months. Soiling accumulation was characterized via morphological, elemental, and structural analyses.

Surface morphology was analyzed using a field-emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM, ZEISS Sigma 360 VP) after gold sputtering. EDX analysis (Oxford Instruments, AZtecLiveLite) provided semi-quantitative elemental composition. Mineralogy of dust collected after 3 months was studied by powder X-ray diffraction (Bruker AXS D8 Advance, CuK α), analyzed with the Rietveld method using TOPAS software and PDF-4 database.

Photovoltaic performance was monitored using two calibrated Si reference photocells (Si-V-10TC-T) on the same tilt/orientation as test modules (Fig. 2c). One cell was cleaned daily; the other remained soiled. Soiling Ratio (SR) was calculated as:

$$SR = \frac{I_{Soiled}}{I_{Clean}} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Data were logged at 1-min intervals. Uncertainty in SR was estimated using propagation of uncertainty (GUM) [22], yielding a relative

uncertainty of $\sim 3.67\%$:

$$dSR = \left| \frac{1}{I_{Clean}} \right| dI_{Soiled} + \left| \frac{I_{Soiled}}{(I_{Clean})^2} \right| dI_{Clean} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

An economic model was used to estimate soiling-related losses and cleaning cost-effectiveness, based on a 1 MWp monofacial c-Si PV plant (4826 m², 2223 modules, 450 W, $\eta = 23.5\%$) [23]. A reference annual yield of 2508 MWh was assumed under ideal (no-soiling) conditions [23]. Fig. 3 summarizes the irradiance conditions and main loss mechanisms considered in the financial impact of soiling and the cost-effectiveness of cleaning strategies. In a worst-case scenario (linear soiling, one annual cleaning), soiling losses were monetized using a fixed electricity price (60 USD/MWh). Cumulative Financial Loss (CFL) was computed as.

$$CFL(t) = \sum_{i=1}^t (E_{ideal,i} \cdot S_i \cdot P_{elec}) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Cleaning costs were gathered from regional service providers (Table 1). Dry cleaning (~ 0.16 USD/m²) and wet cleaning (0.13–0.29 USD/m²) were compared. For wet cleaning, 0.7 L/m² water use and 0.18 USD/L base price were assumed, including treatment costs. A delivery distance of 80 km and a total water demand of 3378 m³ were considered for the reference plant.

Cleaning frequency was optimized by applying the Marginal Benefit principle: cleaning is recommended until the benefit of the last cleaning exceeds its cost.

2.2. Controlled indoor replication of desert soiling and cleaning processes

Complementary to the outdoor campaign, accelerated soiling and cleaning experiments were conducted at the indoor soiling laboratory of the French National Institute of Solar Energy (CEA-INES) in Chambéry, France.

The laboratory includes a custom environmental chamber (100 × 60 × 50 cm, Fig. 4) that allows precise control of temperature and relative humidity via PID regulation. Conditions are monitored in real time with GL240 and EL-GFX-2 data loggers. A water-based thermal regulation system independently controls air and sample temperatures. Artificial soiling is generated using an RBG-1000 dust dispenser with standardized Arizona Test Dust (ISO 12103-1), ensuring homogeneous deposition. PV glass samples and mini-modules are mounted on a tiltable plate that can be heated or cooled to reproduce realistic gradients. Experiments reproduced typical desert conditions—arid daytime and nocturnal dew-point cycles—and were followed by cleaning efficiency tests under standardized conditions.

Mini-modules and PV glass coupons (4 × 6 cm) were mounted at 20°

Fig. 2. (a) Atacama Desert Solar Platform (PSDA), where the soiling and cleaning experiments were conducted. (b) Standard photovoltaic (PV) glasses mounted on photovoltaic modules under outdoor exposure conditions. (c) Photocells used for measuring the Soiling Ratio (SR) on the module surface.

Fig. 3. Monthly Plane-of-Array (POA) irradiance on the optimized PV tilt configuration, from PVGIS, and contribution of performance loss factors for the reference PV plant (simulated worst-case scenario using a representative model based on local environmental and operational conditions).

Table 1
Operational cost of dry and wet cleaning methods.

Parameter	Dry cleaning	Wet cleaning
Cost [USD/m ² Panel]	0.16	0.13 to 0.29

tilt, reproducing PSDA installation geometry (Fig. 4 a). After artificial soiling, samples underwent sequential dry and wet cleaning—both common in desert PV systems. Dry cleaning used a 200 rpm mechanical

roller for 2 min, and wet cleaning applied a 2-bar water jet under the same configuration. The mini-modules’ electrical response (I_{sc}) was measured under STC using a Pasan AAA-class simulator [10], and optical transmittance with a Shimadzu UV-2600 spectrophotometer (300–900 nm).

The soiling protocol used real dust collected at PSDA and included three stages: deposition, humidification, and drying (Fig. 5). During these cycles, ambient temperature varied between 22 °C and 30 °C, and relative humidity between 40 % and 90 %, replicating Atacama conditions [15]. The impact on electrical performance was quantified through

a)

b)

Fig. 4. a) Soiling chamber and its different components/features and b) Cleaning chamber: external view (left) and internal view showing cleaning brushes and water nozzles (right).

Fig. 5. Sequence of the dust cementation cycle in the soiling chamber. Reference clean PV minimodule and PV glass samples before exposure. Dust deposition stage on the samples. Humidification under high relative humidity conditions and final drying stage to simulate crust formation.

I_{sc} measurements before and after soiling using a PASAN HighLIGHT SMT + simulator, while adhered mass was obtained from pre- and post-exposure weight differences [15].

In the second phase, samples were cleaned using dry and wet methods [24,25]. Tests were performed in the cleaning chamber (24 °C, 20° tilt; Fig. 4 b). Dry cleaning involved two 200 rpm passes—one unidirectional and one bidirectional—while wet cleaning applied a 2-bar jet for 2 min. I–V curves were recorded after each dry pass and post wet-cleaning. Each method was repeated five times using 10 g of dust per test. Cleaning efficiency was calculated as the ratio of recovered I_{sc}

in [A] to reference current:

$$Cleaning\ efficiency = \frac{I_{sc\ after\ cleaning}}{I_{sc\ reference}} \times 100\% \tag{Eq. 4}$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Chemical composition of soiling

The XRD analysis (Fig. 6) was performed on the material collected at the end of the three-month exposure period, once the accumulated dust

Fig. 6. a) XRD pattern of dust deposited on the surface of PV modules after 3 months of exposure. b) Distribution of mineral phases identified, including quartz, albite and gypsum, among others.

mass had reached the necessary intensity and resolution for a pattern to be obtained. The resulting diffractogram reflects the crystalline composition of the consolidated deposit, providing reliable characterization of the accumulated material and mineral assembly present on the surface. The diffractogram reveals characteristic minerals of the Atacama Desert [26–28]. The identified phases were albite ($\text{NaAl}_{0.91}\text{Si}_3\text{O}_8$), muscovite ($\text{KAl}_2(\text{Si}_3\text{Al})\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH},\text{F})_2$), quartz (SiO_2), gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), clinocllore ($(\text{Mg},\text{Fe},\text{Al})_6(\text{Si},\text{Al})_4\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH})_8$), kaolinite ($\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_4$), orthoclase ($(\text{K}_{0.88}\text{Na}_{0.1}\text{Ca}_{0.01}\text{Ba}_{0.01})\text{Al}_{1.005}\text{Si}_{2.995}\text{O}_8$), and hematite (Fe_2O_3). These phases reflect the heterogeneous nature of the deposited material. Crystalline quantification performed through the Rietveld refinement method, indicates that the predominant phase is albite (36 %), followed by muscovite (26 %). Minor phases include quartz (14 %) and clinocllore (13 %). Additionally, orthoclase (5 %), hematite (2 %), kaolinite-1A (2 %), and gypsum (2 %) were identified (Fig. 6b). This information provides a solid basis for comparison with other microstructural and surface adhesion studies reported in the literature [15,16] and is consistent with previous studies conducted at the PSDA site, showing that the mineral composition of the accumulated soiling has not changed significantly over the years [15, 16]. The persistence of the same mineral assemblage indicates that the PSDA environment is dominated by locally derived particulate material, with no significant external inputs that could alter its composition [29, 30]. The similarity among diffraction patterns further confirms the mineralogical consistency of the PSDA site, where the recurrent presence of silicates, feldspars, and sulphates defines a stable crystalline assemblage characteristic of soiling layers formed under the arid conditions of the Atacama Desert.

Although XRD analysis provides a representative crystalline composition of the deposited dust at PSDA, it offers only a static view of the system. To understand the processes governing particle adhesion and surface consolidation, the morphological and chemical evolution must be examined over time. The combination of SEM and EDX measurements on samples collected at different times enable the analysis of the progressive formation and growth of cemented structures including variations in texture, particle distribution and elemental association. This complementary approach links the mineral composition identified by XRD with the surface cementation mechanisms that occur under natural soiling conditions.

3.2. Morphological and chemical evolution of soiling

Fig. 7 presents FE-SEM micrographs showing the progressive transition from initial deposition (2 days) to cohesive crust formation (3

months).

Within the first two days, the glass surface remains practically clean, showing a small number of randomly dispersed particles. At 100 μm , the low material density and wide spacing between grains indicate an initial stage of dry deposition, dominated by physical mechanisms of gravitational settling, impact, and electrostatic adhesion. At 10 μm , small aggregates are observed, where incipient and eroded prismatic structures without a defined geometry or preferred orientation. Their irregular contours and lack of bridges confirm a dispersed, physical accumulation without chemical bonding.

By day 7, the surface shows increased particle density and more homogeneous distribution. At 10 μm , well-defined prismatic microstructures grow from crystallization nuclei formed by the initial eroded particles. This marks the onset of cementation, with compact groupings and reduced particle individuality.

After one month, a more homogeneous texture develops due to increased bonding. At 10 μm , well-developed prismatic crystals (10–17 μm) grow laterally and vertically, forming more stable clusters.

By the second month, the glass is completely covered. At 100 μm , compact aggregates and laminar structures reduce surface porosity. At 10 μm , prismatic crystals act as a structural matrix that traps fine particles, increasing cohesion and promoting consolidation.

After three months, the glass shows large areas. At 100 μm , a homogeneous coverage is observed, with dense regions where the boundaries between individual aggregates begin to disappear, resulting in a more uniform surface. At 10 μm , the material shows a compact, geometry-less structure indicating advanced consolidation into a cohesive mass.

To explain bonding mechanisms, EDX elemental mapping was performed alongside XRD and SEM.

Fig. 8 shows the elemental distribution. During the first two days, localized Ca and S areas appear, associated with gypsum. They promote the formation of early gypsum nuclei, preceding cohesive prism growth.

In later stages, sulfate phases grow and silicates (quartz) are incorporated, increasing heterogeneity. Humidity cycles reinforce gypsum crystal growth and mineral mixing [31]. After 3 months, prisms lose definition and form a continuous crust dominated by sulphates. According to Meldrum and O'Shaughnessy [32], growth under confinement.

Overall, the XRD, SEM, and EDX analyses confirm that surface cementation begins in the first days of exposure, driven by the presence of calcium sulfates acting as primary binding phases. Over time, these compounds promote the growth and interconnection of prismatic gypsum structures, integrating silicate particles into a continuous crust. This

Fig. 7. Time-resolved Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) analysis of the morphological evolution leading to the onset of surface cementation (2 days–3 months).

Fig. 8. Temporal evolution of surface cementation revealed by Energy-Dispersive X-ray (EDX) elemental mapping and Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) images, showing the progressive growth of Ca–S-rich gypsum phases leading to the formation of a continuous crust.

progressive consolidation enhances the mechanical stability and adhesion of the deposit, explaining the formation of persistent mineralized layers on exposed surfaces [33].

3.3. Influence of atmospheric parameters on cementation process

The chemical composition identified through XRD, SEM, and EDX analyses is closely related to the atmospheric conditions that control the dissolution and recrystallization processes of gypsum. To evaluate this influence, continuous monitoring of three key variables, relative humidity (RH), ambient temperature (T_{amb}), and wind speed (WS), was carried out. Recurrent daily patterns were identified that promote the activation of these hygroscopic processes, particularly the formation and consolidation of gypsum. Figs. 9–11 show these data as hourly heatmaps (UTC+0) for the entire three-month exposure period.

Wind speed exhibits a well-defined diurnal pattern (Fig. 9), with calm conditions during the morning and early afternoon, and a gradual increase after 17:00 UTC, reaching values between 8 and 12 $m s^{-1}$. This

evening enhancement corresponds to the period when aeolian transport of dust particles is favored, promoting their deposition on exposed surfaces. Regarding temperature, the records show early morning values below 10 °C and daytime thermal gradients exceeding 20 °C (Fig. 10), conditions that generate thermal contrasts favorable to dissolution and recrystallization processes. Finally, relative humidity (RH) frequently exceeds 60 % during nighttime hours (Fig. 11), contributing to surface hydration and the formation of transient saline solutions. As shown in Fig. 8, the combination of these conditions is sufficient to initiate the partial dissolution of gypsum contained in the atmospheric dust deposited on photovoltaic surfaces [17].

The persistence of elevated night-time relative humidity (above 60 %), in conjunction with sustained high daytime air temperature values (above 25 °C), activates a daily cycle of surface hydration, partial salt dissolution and subsequent dehydration (evaporation). This process, clearly illustrated in the temperature and humidity heatmaps (Figs. 10 and 11), promotes the formation of transient saline solutions. Upon drying, these solutions facilitate the recrystallization of gypsum on

Fig. 9. Hourly heatmaps of wind speed recorded at the PSDA between February and April 2025. Note that the time stamp is Coordinated Universal Time (UTC+0); the local time, depending on the date, is approximately UTC–5.

Fig. 10. Hourly heatmaps of air temperature (b) recorded at the PSDA between February and April 2025. Note that the time stamp is Coordinated Universal Time (UTC+0); the local time, depending on the date, is approximately UTC-5.

Fig. 11. Hourly heatmaps of relative humidity recorded at the PSDA between February and April 2025. Note that the time stamp is Coordinated Universal Time (UTC+0); the local time, depending on the date, is approximately UTC-5.

exposed surfaces. Although RH slightly decreases in April compared to February, early-morning minima near 5 °C still coincide with RH > 50 % (Figs. 10 and 11). These conditions remain favorable for the hygroscopic cycle responsible for gypsum recrystallization [34]. The persistence of these factors, combined with a stable atmosphere and an absence of precipitation events, enables the cementation process to continue actively, as reflected in the morphological evolution observed via SEM.

The observed atmospheric conditions define a functional cementation loop comprising the following steps: (i) moisture absorption; (ii) partial salt dissolution; (iii) accelerated evaporation; and (iv) localized recrystallization [32]. Persistent cemented structures form with the daily repetition of this cycle, as illustrated in Figs. 7 and 8. The absence of rainfall and the presence of high solar radiation throughout the period ensure that this mechanism remains active without external disturbance [31,35]. The stable atmospheric regime observed at PSDA, characterized by consistent diurnal cycles of evening breeze (Fig. 9), daily temperature

(Fig. 10) and nocturnal relative humidity (Fig. 11), directly explains the microscale transformations identified through XRD, SEM, and EDX analyses. These moderate and repetitive conditions promoted the daily dissolution and recrystallization of gypsum, as evidenced by the progressive increase of Ca and S signals and the morphological transition from isolated crystallization nuclei to cohesive surface crusts. The results confirm that surface cementation in the Atacama Desert is not driven by extreme climatic events but rather by the persistence of cyclic, hygroscopic processes that control the growth and consolidation of gypsum on exposed photovoltaic surfaces.

3.4. Effects of soiling on PV modules under outdoor conditions at the PSDA

The weekly evolution of Soiling Ratio (SR), shown in Fig. 12, indicates a sustained loss of optical performance during the three months

of exposure at PSDA, with a slope of -0.827% per month ($R^2 = 0.773$). During the monitored period, the heat maps of relative humidity, temperature, and wind speed showed atmospheric stability, characterized by nights with relative humidity above 60 %, diurnal thermal oscillations close to 20 °C, and moderate winds (see Figs. 9–11). Thus, the SR rate is primarily associated with local climatic cycles rather than punctual or seasonal events that favor self-cleaning mechanisms. The absence of precipitation reinforces the hypothesis that SR decay is a direct consequence of these persistent conditions, which are responsible for 77.3 % of the observed trend.

This soiling pattern indicates that the combination of soluble salts, high nocturnal humidity and diurnal thermal variations generate cemented deposits on the PV modules and in the surrounding soil. Furthermore, Olivares et al. [26] documented the recrystallization of hygroscopic salts in the form of cohesive crusts in the sedimentary matrix. The occurrence of cementation mechanisms in both substrates confirms that local physicochemical conditions (as the presence of salts) environmental humidity and temperature oscillations are key factors in the level of adhesion of the deposited material. To provide a broader context for these results, they can be compared with data recorded in other arid regions. The NREL Soiling Map shows rates between -0.33% and 0.58% per month in arid areas of south-western USA [33]. In high irradiance sites as southern Italy and Nicosia, (Cyprus), the IEA-PVPS reports losses of 6.9 % and 16 % per month, respectively [33,36,37]. Thus, the soiling rate at PSDA is low compared to other desertic regions, implying that cementation is a limiting factor in the accumulation of loose dust.

Even though the soiling rate at the PSDA is low, the persistence of cemented deposits can lead to sustained optical losses and, consequently, influence operational costs. The cleaning cost was set at 1110 USD/MWp for wet cleaning and 444 USD/MWp for dry cleaning, both considered as outsourced services. Dry cleaning services represent approximately 40 % of the total cost of wet cleaning. Although they eliminate water purchase and transportation expenses, their operational considerations include the amortization of cleaning robots, additional equipment logistics, and the service provider's profit margin. It is worth noting that the cleaning costs reported in this study are higher than those in regions such as Saudi Arabia [38], India, and China, where labor is generally less expensive, but comparable to those observed in the United States [39] and Europe [40], largely due to water and transportation costs in the Atacama Desert.

Cleaning intervals of equal duration were evaluated to determine the

frequency of dry and wet cleaning cycles that maintain a positive marginal benefit. The optimal schedule resulted in five wet cleanings per year (every 73 days, starting on April 18) and fourteen dry cleanings per year (every 26 days, starting on May 31). Dry cleaning does not remove the nucleation layer formed on the module surface and was assumed to achieve a 98 % cleaning efficiency. Under these conditions, the inherent energy loss associated with the uncleaned interval was 1.96 % for wet cleaning and 0.7 % for dry cleaning.

Given these results, and considering the cementation phenomena observed in desertic environments, at least one annual wet cleaning is recommended as a restoration strategy. Therefore, a combined strategy of one wet cleaning and twelve dry cleanings per year, spaced approximately every 28 days, is suggested as the most effective operational approach. This is in line with Ilse et al. [39] who emphasize that the choice between dry cleaning, wet cleaning or automated systems should be based on a detailed knowledge of the nature of the soiling.

3.5. Indoor replication of PSDA soiling and cleaning mechanism

The results obtained from the outdoor experiments were used to configure and validate the laboratory tests. Meteorological parameters recorded at the PSDA, together with the morphological and chemical features identified by SEM analyses, defined the operating conditions of the soiling chamber developed by CEA-INES [10]. Under these controlled settings, the humidification and drying cycles characteristic of the PSDA environment were reproduced to simulate the hygroscopic processes that drive sulfate dissolution and recrystallization, leading to the formation of prismatic gypsum structures. FE-SEM micrographs (Fig. 13) show well-defined prisms and compact aggregates closely resembling the morphology of outdoor samples after two months of exposure, corresponding to an advanced cementation stage. These results confirm that the chamber reliably replicates the gypsum-induced cementation process through precise control of humidity and temperature, providing a consistent basis for evaluating cleaning strategies.

Once the cementation process was reproduced under controlled conditions, the next step was to examine the material's response to different cleaning strategies. The presence of cemented deposits with high surface cohesion represents one of the main challenges for maintaining photovoltaic systems in desert environments, as their removal often requires more intensive and costly methods. In this context, indoor experiments offer a significant advantage: they allow the acceleration of processes that occur slowly and depend on climatic variability under

Fig. 12. Evolution of the Soiling Ratio (SR) measured by photocells during three months of exposure at the PSDA.

Fig. 13. FE-SEM micrographs of the cemented material obtained under controlled indoor conditions using the CEA-INES soiling chamber. The images show the formation of prismatic gypsum crystals ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and compact aggregates produced after reproducing typical humidification–drying cycles observed at the PSDA site.

outdoor conditions, enabling a detailed assessment of the physical and chemical mechanisms involved in removal. Following this approach, the laboratory tests focused on comparing the effectiveness of dry and wet cleaning methods in eliminating cemented material, considering the adhesion properties and morphology previously characterized at the PSDA.

Fig. 14a presents the results for the dry-cleaning method. The initial short-circuit current (Isc) of a silicon heterojunction mini-module was 8.4 A. the T artificial deposition of 10 g of dust, repeated five times per sample, resulted in Isc average reduction of 7.8 %. As a first cleaning action, a unidirectional roller pass (LR) allowed partial recovery of 98 %; while a second bidirectional pass (LRL) was necessary to reach 98.8 %. Thus, a single mechanical intervention is insufficient to fully remove the accumulated material. These results are consistent with previous studies that report the low effectiveness of dry cleaning against deposits with high surface cohesion [30,41].

In contrast to dry cleaning, the wet cleaning method showed higher effectiveness in the recovery of Isc, reaching 99.9 % of the initial value after a single cleaning (Fig. 14 b). Although the loss induced by the deposit was slightly higher (8.3 %), the use of pressurized water restored almost all the original electrical performance. This comparison between both cleaning methods demonstrates that water not only physically removes the accumulated material but also enables the partial dissolution of salts and soluble compounds present in cemented layers. This dual action is especially effective against deposits with high surface cohesion, which tend to resist the mechanical action of dry methods. The

ability to achieve high levels of recovery in a single cycle makes wet cleaning a technically robust alternative; however, its implementation may be limited not only by water scarcity but also by logistical restrictions, operational costs, and the need for water storage, filtration, and recycling systems in plants located in desert or remote areas [42, 43].

To verify the consistency of the Isc-based evaluation, the obtained flash-test data were analyzed to extract maximum power (Pmax) values for the same cleaning trials. Fig. 15 shows the boxplots of normalized Pmax for wet- and dry-cleaning tests.

The results confirm that the evolution of Pmax closely follows the trend observed for Isc, indicating that optical attenuation caused by cemented soiling is the dominant mechanism behind power loss. Before cleaning, the cemented deposits induced average Pmax reductions of approximately 10.2 % (wet-cleaning tests) and 9.3 % (dry-cleaning tests). After cleaning, the wet method restored 99.5 % ± 0.2 % of the reference power output, while dry cleaning reached 98.9 % ± 0.4 %. The slight residual difference (≈0.5–1 %) reflects the influence of micro-residues and incomplete removal of strongly adhered particles, consistent with the SEM and EDX observations previously discussed.

These findings validate the robustness of the Isc-based assessment and demonstrate that cemented soiling primarily affects optical transmission rather than resistive or electronic properties of the cells. The narrow post-cleaning distributions in Fig. 8 also highlight the repeatability of the flash-test measurements. This agreement between Isc and Pmax further reinforces the reliability of the dual-site experimental

Fig. 14. Boxplot analysis of normalized short-circuit current (Isc) for dry-cleaning (a) and wet-cleaning (b) experiments under controlled indoor conditions. The results are expressed as percentages relative to the clean reference.

Fig. 15. Boxplot analysis of normalized maximum power (P_{max}) for dry-cleaning (left) and wet-cleaning (right) experiments under controlled indoor conditions. Blue labels indicate the average power recovery relative to the clean reference.

methodology and aligns with previous reports by Refs. [44–46], which emphasize the value of combining both electrical parameters for comprehensive soiling evaluation.

In the context of cemented materials such as those observed at PSDA, the selection of the cleaning method must consider both the recovery of electrical performance and its impact on the evolution of the deposit. Morphological and chemical analyses using XRD, SEM, and EDX (Figs. 4–6) revealed that the deposited material contains crystallization nuclei rich in calcium and sulfur, which promote the formation of dense surface layers prone to recrystallization. If not entirely removed by dry cleaning, these residues may act as seeds for new crystallization cycles under conditions of high nocturnal humidity and large diurnal temperature swings (Fig. 7). This process increases the difficulty of removal during subsequent cleanings and contributes to the long-term consolidation of the deposit, affecting optical transmittance and the integrity of the glass. In addition, the remaining particles act as abrasive agents during successive brush passes, generating microdamage by friction and reducing the service life of the surface [47,48].

The persistence of these cemented deposits also impacts operational costs. According to Ilse et al., cleaning costs vary significantly worldwide, ranging from less than 0.05 USD/m² in regions such as India, Egypt, or Saudi Arabia to nearly 1 USD/m² in countries like Germany or the Netherlands, depending on water availability, labor, logistics, and local regulations [39,48]. In the Atacama Desert, values between 0.16 and 0.29 USD/m² fall within the lower range of global records, although costs can increase when more frequent or specialized cleaning is required to address cemented layers.

To improve the efficiency and sustainability of maintenance, recent studies have explored solutions that combine technological innovation with operational optimization [49]. These include automated cleaning systems capable of detaching adhered deposits, predictive models to optimize cleaning frequency, and superhydrophobic coatings that reduce surface energy and particles' adhesion. Complementary to these advances, the integration of outdoor experiments with indoor accelerated soiling tests offers a powerful methodological framework. The accelerated system reproduced, in just a few days, the soiling and cleaning mechanisms that required nearly three months of outdoor exposure, significantly shortening study time while generating controlled and reproducible data to support predictive and decision-making models. This integrated approach establishes a robust basis to design precise, efficient, and context-adapted cleaning strategies, particularly in regions where dust cementation represents a recurring operational challenge.

4. Conclusions

This study analyzed the behavior of cemented soiling on

photovoltaic modules installed at the Atacama Desert Solar Platform, through a morphological and compositional characterization of the deposited material, as well as experimental cleaning tests under controlled conditions. The results obtained allow for an understanding of the cementation formation process and its effect on electrical performance and the economic losses of the PV system.

The first signs of cementation appeared on the second day of exposure, when prismatic particles enriched in calcium and sulfur were found to be adhering to the glass. By the seventh day, SEM and EDX analyses revealed well-defined gypsum crystalline structures to have developed. This mineral acts as a crystallization nucleus that functions as an active centre for mineral aggregation. Under favorable environmental conditions, such as high relative humidity and diurnal thermal oscillations, these nuclei trigger daily cycles of dissolution and recrystallization that progressively consolidate the growth of the cemented deposit.

The results obtained at PSDA indicate a sustained loss of optical performance during the first three months of exposure, with a soiling-induced optical degradation rate of -0.827% per month ($R^2 = 0.773$). This is attributed to stable atmospheric conditions characterized by high nocturnal humidity and diurnal thermal oscillations, accounting for 77.3 % of the total. While the accumulated soiling level was low compared to other arid regions worldwide, the presence of cemented deposits indicates a progressive adhesion dynamic driven by recrystallization processes, amplifying the long-term energy and economic impact. Under a linear accumulation model, an annual reduction in energy generation of 9.8 % is estimated (≈ 98 MWh/year per 10 MW plant), resulting in normalized economic losses of over USD 93,800 per MW per year in the context of the Atacama Desert.

Indoor tests carried out under controlled conditions demonstrated that water-based cleaning is substantially more effective than dry cleaning for cemented deposits such as those observed at PSDA. While wet cleaning restored 99.9 % of I_{sc} and 99.5 % of P_{max} in a single cycle, dry cleaning achieved 98.8 % and 98.9 %, respectively, after two passes. The close correlation between I_{sc} and P_{max} validates the robustness of the electrical assessment and confirms that cemented soiling primarily impacts optical transmission rather than electronic parameters. However, beyond the immediate electrical recovery, morphological and chemical analyses revealed that dry cleaning does not fully remove the cemented particles, leaving behind residues that act as crystallization nuclei. These residual traces promote new cementation cycles under favorable environmental conditions, increasing material adhesion in subsequent events. This cumulative effect complicates future maintenance tasks and reinforces the need to select cleaning strategies that restore optical performance and minimize nucleation and deposit evolution over time. In this context, the choice of cleaning method is strategic: while dry cleaning is more economical, it is less effective against

cemented layers. In contrast, wet cleaning achieves better technical results but is constrained by operational costs and the availability of water resources. These findings highlight the importance of adapting maintenance strategies to the type of deposit, considering technical, economic and environmental factors, to ensure the efficiency and sustainability of PV systems.

Overall, the novelty of this work lies in bridging the gap between field and laboratory investigations of cemented soiling, thereby providing both mechanistic understanding and actionable recommendations. By demonstrating how gypsum-driven recrystallization cycles accelerate crust formation and by quantifying both technical and economic impacts, this study establishes a reference for developing maintenance protocols tailored to desert PV systems. These findings extend beyond the Atacama context, offering a transferable methodology for studying and mitigating cementation-driven soiling in other arid and semi-arid regions.

Future research should aim to determine the critical thresholds at which cementation is triggered, quantify the long-term evolution of energy and financial losses under different cleaning scenarios, and optimize less abrasive, more selective cleaning methods against deposits with high surface cohesion. Exploring surface treatments or coatings that hinder the initial adhesion of particles is also essential, particularly in environments with high concentrations of soluble salts and nocturnal humidity. Addressing these challenges will facilitate the development of more effective, durable solutions adapted to desert environments, where mitigating soiling is crucial for maintaining efficiency and prolonging the service life of PV systems.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

D. Olivares: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **J. Montoya:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **A. Marzo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **D. Soler:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **J. Llanos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **J. Rakotoniaina:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **H. Colin:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis. **I. Tsanakas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Formal analysis. **J. Aïme:** Validation, Resources, Project administration. **N. Torres:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **V. del Campo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank Grant RYC2021-031958-I funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the European Union “NextGenerationEU/PRTR”; ANID/FONDAP/1523A0006 “Solar Energy Research Center” SERC-Chile; the Chilean Economic Development Agency (CORFO), contract No. 17PTCECS-75830 for the project “AtaMoS TeC”; ANID–Fondecyt 1251918; and the ECOS-ANID cooperation program C21E08. Additional support was provided by Engineering Project 2030 Code 16ENI2-71940. The authors also acknowledge the Unidad de

Equipamiento Científico MAINI at Universidad Católica del Norte for supporting sample preparation and data generation through X-ray diffraction (XRD) facilities. This work further benefited from the equipment acquired through ANID’s Concurso Equipamiento Científico y Tecnológico FONDEQUIP Mediano 2022, EQM 220028 “Adquisición de un Microscopio Electrónico FE-SEM para el fortalecimiento de la investigación, vinculación y docencia de pre y postgrado de la Universidad de Antofagasta. We gratefully acknowledge the Laboratory for Territorial Characterization and Radiometry at the Centro de Desarrollo Energético de Antofagasta (CDEA) for providing the infrastructure and technical facilities essential for this study. We also thank the Solar Energy PhD Program at the University of Antofagasta for its academic support throughout the research process. The authors want to acknowledge the CACTUS project funded by the European Commission in the HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-06 program (Ref.: 101132182), And Transferencia ruta solar e hidrogeno verde en la región de Antofagasta: una planificación estratégica para el desarrollo energético local. BIP 40067568–0 Gobierno Regional de Antofagasta.

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